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The Negative Judgment on Future Prospects in the Italian Regions During the Period 2012-2022

It decreased on average by 41.56% between 2012 and 2022 in the Italian regions

Istat calculates the value of the negative opinion on future prospects in the Italian regions. The variable is calculated as the percentage of people aged 14 and over who believe that their personal situation will worsen in the next 5 years out of the total number of people aged 14 and over.

Ranking of the Italian regions by value of negative opinion on future prospects in 2022. The Marche is in first place for negative opinion on future prospects in 2022 with an amount equal to 18.1 units, followed by Friuli Venezia Giulia with 165.6 and by Molise with a value of 16.3. In the middle of the table are Valle d'Aosta with a value of 14.3 units, followed by Veneto with a value of 14.00 units and Calabria with a value of 13.7 units. Sardinia closes the ranking with a value of 9.9 units, followed by Campania with a value of 9.4 units and Basilicata with 8.5 units.

Ranking of the Italian regions by percentage change in the negative opinion on future prospects between 2012 and 2022. Friuli Venezia Giulia is in first place for the value of the percentage change in the negative opinion on future prospects between 2012 and 2022 with a value equal to -20.95%. Marche follows with a variation equal to an amount of -24.27% corresponding to a reduction from an amount of 23.9 units up to a value of 18.1 units equal to an amount of -5.8 units. In third place Trentino Alto Adige with a variation equal to an amount of -25.47% corresponding to a reduction from an amount of 16.1 units up to a value of 12.00 units. Piedmont is mid-table with a value equal to -36.29% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 23.7 units up to a value of 15.1 units equal to an amount of -8.6 units. Calabria follows with a variation of -36.87% corresponding to an amount from 21.7 units up to a value of 13.7 units. Lombardy follows with a variation of -38.04% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 18.4 units up to a value of 11.4 units. Sardinia closes the ranking with a value of -56.96% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 23 units up to 9.9 units. In penultimate place Puglia with a value equal to -61.71% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 26.9 units up to a value of 10.3 units. Campania closes the ranking with a variation of -64.66% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 26.6 units up to a value of 9.4 units. Between 2012 and 2022, the negative opinion on future prospects in the Italian regions decreased on average by 41.56% in the Italian regions.

The negative opinion on future prospects in the Italian macro-regions between 2012 and 2022. The negative opinion on future prospects decreased in all Italian macro-regions. Specifically, this value decreased by 35.4% in the North-East, by 35.85% in the North, by 36.63% in the North-West, by 44.92% in the Centre, by 52.99% in the Islands, of 55.86% in the South, of 57.37% for the South. The value of the negative opinion on future prospects however shows a significant gap between North and South. In fact, the central-northern regions tend to have a level of negative on future prospects, higher than in the southern regions. In particular, the value of the negative opinion on future prospects

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in the North-East is 29.20% higher than the corresponding value in the South. Similar values are also found in the North with +20.35%, the North-West with +13.27%, and in the Central Italy with +24.78%.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. A clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient is presented below. The data highlights the presence of two clusters:

- Cluster 1: Sardinia, Lombardy, Basilicata, Trentino Alto Adige, Campania, Lazio, Abruzzo, Calabria, Puglia;
- Cluster 2: Piedmont, Umbria, Marche, Tuscany, Liguria, Sicily, Emilia-Romagna, Molise, Friuli Venezia Giulia, Veneto, Valle d'Aosta.

Considering the average value of the clusters by value of the negative opinion on future prospects, the following ordering of the clusters results: $C2 > C1$. We can see that the clusters are very heterogeneous. In fact, both Cluster 1 and Cluster 2 are made up of regions that are very different from each other both in terms of GDP per capita, geographical affiliation and also socio-economic condition. Therefore it is not possible to identify economic, social or cultural elements that could justify the belonging of a certain region to one cluster rather than another. To have a clustering that can be better interpreted from a socio-economic and cultural-institutional point of view, it is necessary to increase the number of clusters from an amount of $k=2$, up to a value of $k=4$. However, it must be considered that by setting $k=4$ one renounces the choice of the optimal value of k based on the level of the Silhouette coefficient which in this case is equal to $k=2$.

Therefore, setting $k=4$ we can note the following groupings:

- Cluster 1: Campania, Sardinia, Basilicata, Lazio, Abruzzo, Calabria, Puglia, Lombardy;
- Cluster 2: Emilia Romagna, Friuli Venezia Giulia, Veneto, Piedmont, Tuscany, Valle d'Aosta;
- Cluster 3: Marche, Sicily, Molise, Liguria, Umbria;
- Cluster 4: Trentino Alto Adige.

If we consider the average value of the variable for the individual clusters we obtain the following ordering detected in 2021, namely: $C2 > C3 > C4 > C1$. In this way we can have greater clarity regarding the geographical structure of the distribution of the observed variable. In fact, we note that the first cluster for the value of the negative opinion on future prospects in the Italian regions is made up of cluster 2 in which we can find 5 regions of the North and one region of the South. On the contrary, we can note that the last cluster for the value of the negative opinion on future prospects it is made up of cluster 1 essentially made up of the southern regions to which Lazio and Lombardy are added.

Conclusions. We can note that the value of the negative judgment on future prospects decreased in all Italian regions and macro-regions between 2012 and 2022. However, there are some relevant differences between the Italian regions. In fact, the regions of the Centre-North tend to have a much higher level of negative expectations about the future than the regions of the South, with the exception of Lombardy and Lazio. That is, regions that have high per capita incomes tend to express much more significant negative future expectations than regions that have low per capita incomes. It follows that perceptions about future economic conditions could be characterized by certain cognitive biases independent of real socio-economic and financial conditions.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Appendix

Regioni	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Piemonte	23,7	27	18,7	18,2	15,9	17,5	14,7	12,9	16,1	13,1	15,1
Valle d'Aosta	22,3	19,6	17,8	16,3	17,4	12,5	13,3	12,3	13,9	12,4	14,3
Liguria	21,1	24	22,8	18,4	15,7	16	15,5	15,3	13,9	12	15,2
Lombardia	18,4	18,9	15,1	14,9	14,5	13,2	12,8	10,4	11,6	9,2	11,4
Trentino-Alto Adige	16,1	15,8	13,4	11,7	11	11,3	9,1	9	11,2	9,9	12
Veneto	21,8	22,4	17,3	17	16,1	16,5	12,8	13,5	13,1	11,7	14
Friuli-Venezia Giulia	21	20,8	18,2	14,9	17,4	16,8	13,3	11,7	15,4	13,3	16,6
Emilia-Romagna	25,3	25,9	17	16,5	13,6	17,6	12,7	15,3	14,5	12,1	15,3
Toscana	30,1	27,9	18,1	19	18,1	16,6	13,8	13,7	17,4	10,6	15,2
Umbria	23	28,2	21,6	17,2	18	18,3	15,1	14	14,8	11,4	14,7
Marche	23,9	25,6	22,9	23,7	17,8	18,5	14,7	15	16	13,2	18,1
Lazio	23,4	22	16,4	17,6	16,2	12,9	15,1	10,8	11,2	10,6	12,3
Abruzzo	20,8	23,1	18,3	17	15,6	16,6	13,8	10,2	11,9	9,5	12,5
Molise	22,2	21,5	19,8	21,4	17,7	17,7	16,5	13	9,4	11,8	16,3
Campania	26,6	21,8	19,2	17	13,9	12,9	12,2	10,5	8,9	7,5	9,4

Puglia	26,9	26,6	21	17,5	14	15	12,7	11,1	12,2	9,2	10,3
Basilicata	19,7	17,8	20,3	15,6	15	13,1	10,6	9,3	11,6	9,9	8,5
Calabria	21,7	22,4	18,7	18,6	14,4	16	11,1	13,3	13	8,4	13,7
Sicilia	28	27,8	19,8	21,6	15,4	19,1	15,8	12,3	12,5	8,1	13,4
Sardegna	23	18,6	14,6	14,7	14,5	13,9	12,5	9	9,1	8,7	9,9

	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Nord	21,2	22,2	16,9	16,1	15,0	15,4	13,1	12,4	13,3	11,1	13,6
Nord-ovest	20,2	21,6	16,9	16,2	15,1	14,6	13,6	11,6	13,0	10,5	12,8
Nord-est	22,6	23,0	16,9	16,1	14,8	16,5	12,5	13,6	13,7	11,8	14,6
Centro	25,6	24,8	18,1	18,8	17,1	15,2	14,6	12,5	14,0	11,0	14,1
Mezzogiorno	25,6	24,0	19,3	18,2	14,6	15,5	13,2	11,2	11,1	8,4	11,3
Sud	25,1	23,2	19,6	17,4	14,3	14,4	12,4	11,0	10,8	8,5	10,7
Isole	26,8	25,5	18,5	19,9	15,2	17,8	14,9	11,5	11,7	8,3	12,6
Italia	23,6	23,3	18,0	17,4	15,3	15,4	13,4	12,0	12,7	10,2	12,9

